
**System and Elements, Control and Management of Election Fraud -
Tool of Global Masonic Mafia_Driven Elite *and* its Deep State -
Imitation Democracy and Management and Control *Respective*
State and Examples of The US Elections 2020**

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ABSTRACT: Lord prof PhD PhD Momtchil Dobrev-Halachev developed 2010 “Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism” as a based principle materialism since more than 17 century., 2010 “Theory and practice of the Mafiotismus” and 2001 “Theory of the mafia ”. The 2020 US elections have proven exactly how the falsification scheme, fraud in elections organized by the elite, the oligarchy, the kleptocracy and the mafia in the United States works. This mafia, which aims at the NEW WORLD ORDER and the enslavement of the entire planet and all nations. As president, Trump opposed this mafia, but it tricked him into rigging the election.

KEYWORDS: Elections 2020 USA, Mafia,

1. INTRODUCTION

In the year 2010 Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed the ‘Theory of Mafiotismus’ as a new state niveau based on private and personal interests of the prime-minister, ministers, government .. Based on this “Theory of Mafiotismus” Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed 2010 the “Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism” as a based principle materialism since more than 17 century.

In the year 2001 Lord Prof. Momtchil DObrev developed the Theory of the mafia and Theory of corruption. All the both theories has been developed by analyzing the mafia and the corruption all over the world. .

In this article we analyze all types of mafipulations and falsifications in one election - types, elements that serve the global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state.

In this article we give a brief overview of the tasks, goals of the deep state and the global Masonic mafia-ruled elite.

And as an example, the elections in the USA 2020 proved exactly and clearly how the scheme of falsification, fraud of the elections organized by the elite, oligarchy, kleptocracy and mafia in the USA works. This mafia, which aims at the NEW WORLD ORDER and the enslavement of the entire planet and all nations. As president, Trump opposed this mafia, but it tricked him into rigging the election.

In this article we analyze and reveal all the falsifications and frauds that took place during the US 2020 elections on November 3, 2020. The falsifications and frauds were committed by the elite, oligarchy, kleptocracy and the US mafia - representatives of the Financial Banking Resource Technology Mafia MATERIALISM.

In this article we analyze all types of manipulations and falsifications in one choice - types, elements.

President Trump jumped on this elite, the oligarchy, from 2016 to 2020. President Trump thwarted the plans of the oligarchy, in many areas. Apart from the fact that this oligarchy prepared for him both the pandemic, Kovid 19, and the falsification of the 2020 elections.

1.1 Introduce the Problem

In reality, for a proper understanding of the causes, grounds for the falsifications and frauds of the 2020 elections in the United States, we need a more thorough analysis of the situation, the falsifications, the methods, the schemes, the organization itself.

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2. RESEARCH METHODS

Research methods of occurrence of Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism and the MAFIOTISMUS, its logic of work, of existence, of management and its execution by activities by their representatives.

Research methods of the plan of the Global Masonic mafia elite, oligarchy and plutocracy to govern every country in the world, with the ultimate goal of profit from that country in every way.

In reality, this is a process of imposing the NEW HOLOCAUST, GENOCIDE AND DICTATORSHIP OF DIGITAL MAFIOTISM.

Analysis of the essence of the global Masonic mafia elite.

Structure of this elite.

Composition of this elite.

Analysis of the deep state, principles, goals, state, organization.

Analysis of the electoral process, the elections in each country.

Analysis of the system of election fraud.

Analysis of the types of election fraud.

Analysis of the different variants, possibilities for rigging elections.

Analysis of the state structures that support this process.

Analysis of the state structures that are used for repression.

Analysis of the court and pressure on the court and judges to abdicate the court from the control of the election process.

Analysis of the Prosecutor's Office and pressure on prosecutors to abdicate the prosecution from the control of the election process.

3. PRINCIPLES OF THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA-DRIVEN ELITE AND THE DEEP STATE GOVERNED BY IT - A BRIEF DESCRIPTION, CONCEPT, CONTENT, AND OF THE GLOBAL MASONIC ELITE

The global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state ruled by it is a corporate, militarized, functionally defined, mafia group of people who manage and own financial, banking, corporate, IT companies, not elected by the citizen states, which actually govern not only a specific country, but also a group of countries, on the principles of Mafia and financial banking resource technological mafia Materialism.

The global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state ruled by it have corrupted and mafiotized all spheres of society on which the government of one country, of one union - in the case of the European Commission and the European Union, the USA, and other countries ruled by people of deep country.

All members of the global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state are Freemasons and belong to different secret societies, no matter which. For years, all secret societies have been occupied from within by the representatives and bearers of the goals and aspirations of the Illuminati for a new world genocide and dictatorship over humanity. For these Masons the oath is to obey the law of the lodge and not to comply with any other laws - those of states, international law, unions and others and to do everything in the name and for the benefit of the lodge, observing only the laws of the lodge, but not to the state concerned, to international law, even to commit crimes, to help members of the lodge when they are in trouble, and to carry out the plan of the lodge. All laws and rules are subject to a vow of ideology and faith in Lucifer and the church of Lucifer / Satan.

And the plan is one - to conquer the world, to rule the world by one world government, only by them - the global Masonic mafia elite.

Concept - Prof. Momchil Dobrev

The global Masonic mafia elite and the DEEP STATE ruled by it is an organization, structure, government, of kleptocracy, and cryptocracy of a group of people from the financial banking, resource, technological, corporate elite of the GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIOTIZER of Mafia and the financial bank resource technological mafia Materialism.

AREAS OF GOVERNANCE, CONTROL, OBJECTIVES OF THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIOTIZED ELITE AND THE DEEP STATE MANAGED BY IT, THE MAFIA AND MAFIOTISM

The global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state can be found in all spheres of public life, in all states, governments.

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The spheres of action, goals, tasks, management, control, manifestation of global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state ruled by it and the global Masonic mafia elite through mafia and on the basis of financial banking resource technological mafia Materialism through the mafia are as follows:

-1 /. The sphere of state administration. This includes governments, prime ministers, ministers, government departments and institutions, local authorities and others, their control through compromising and other addictions, sexual addictions and other addictions.

-2 /. The sphere of politics-. This includes parliament, political parties, trade unions, movements, business and non-profit associations, the degradation of the political elite, their control through compromising, and other addictions, sexual addictions and other addictions.

-3 /. Control and management of national security systems, secret services, intelligence services. Control and management of the management and administration of intelligence services, intelligence agencies, internal security departments, space intelligence services, central security services, national security services, intelligence and counterintelligence departments, intelligence departments of the Ministry of Defense, naval intelligence, air services, secret services, secret services

4 /. Control and management of the sphere of military structures, defense structures, defense structures, military-industrial complex

5 /. The sphere of public services - healthcare, education, social assistance, etc.

6 /. The sphere of the private sector, companies, corporations,

7 /. The sphere of the media / radio, television, newspapers, magazines and other media /, their control and management through racketeering, coercion, pressure, sanctions and others.

8 / The sphere of the "civil sector" / civil associations, non-governmental organizations and others /

9 /. Banking and financial sector

10 /. Social networks and information technologies

11 /. The sphere of the judicial system / judges, prosecutors, investigators /, their control through addictions -, bribes, gifts, excursions, control through compromising, and other addictions - sexual, gambling and others.

12 /. The sphere of law enforcement institutions / prosecution, investigation services, police /, their control through addictions, bribes, and others.

13/. Control and management and conquest is the indebtedness of a country through the World Bank, through the International Monetary Fund, the European Central Bank, the International Bank for Settlements and other world banks.

14/. Control and management of monopoly companies, controlling and having monopoly influence all over the world through investment companies, owned by the global Masonic mafia elite - BlackRock and other companies.

15/. Directions and management of state treasury intelligence,

16/. The overthrow of regimes through "yellow", "orange" revolutions and the appointment of governments, presidents to serve the interests of the deep state

17/. Provoking occasions for starting and starting wars against countries whose territories with the respective natural resources are of interest to the representatives of the deep state.

18/. Imposition of policy in the respective countries, which are of the economic interests of the deep state and their profits from it.

19/. Imposition of a policy in the case of NATO for the purpose of threats, wars against third countries from the territories of foreign countries.

20/. Imposing a world government A new world order that will allow them to govern countries, nations, peoples, economies, industries, finances, capital more easily.

21/. Creating conditions, causing chaos through various schemes and occasions - wars, refugee waves, crises - social, social, political, economic, state schemes with the ultimate goal of profits - economic, financial - profit and personal gain.

22/ - Management, control, manipulation, zombieization of the civil society, through non-governmental organizations, their financing / example SOROS /,

23/. Imposing their requirements for military budgets of all countries in order to sell weapons from their companies in the military-industrial complex to countries, countries. 21 /. Control of criminal groups and groups

24/. Control of trade, military, criminal groups, the defense industry, the financial sector, corporate media and counterterrorism.

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25/. Managing the military budgets of states, at least more than half goes to military spending and the purchase of equipment and weapons.

26/. Control and management of the military-industrial complex

27/. Control and management of the state money, budgets, of the respective state

28/. Management of many non-governmental national and international structures - the Council on Foreign Relations, the Royal Institute of International Affairs, the Trust Commission, the Bilderberg Group, the Club of Rome, the Committee 300,

29/. Supranational governance of the countries of the planet.

30/. Management of International Institutions - UN, UNICEF, World Health Organization,

31/. Committing crimes against people, individuals, services

32/. Imposing globalization as an ideology

33/. Imposing the ideology and society of lesbianism, gay, bisexual and transgender people - LGBT as a leader at the state level.

34/. Use of compromising control of individuals - politicians and any others on whom depends the state and other decisions responsible for society as a whole.

35/. Create a program, plan, and accomplish the task of destroying Christianity.

36/. Destruction of the family as a basic building block of society.

37/. Targeted organization of migration through refugee waves, crises

38/. Control and management of the electoral process in each state, imposing organization, management of the electoral process through various schemes of falsification and fraud.

39/. Social terrorism of society from a moral, spiritual, economic point of view.

40/. Total control of the population, by monitoring and controlling the permanent address, social activity on Facebook, Twitter, etc., driving licenses, watched or recorded movies, activity on various blogs, viewing or sending photos, detention by the police, subway trips, credit and debit cards, financial information, viewed photos, sent photos, facial recognition by surveillance cameras, sent e-mails, received emails, searching for information on the network, health card, education, train tickets, bus, plane, recorded mobile applications, used applications, traffic, online transactions, text messages sent, and messages

41 /. Terrorist actions through the US and NATO and other military organizations

42 /. Terrorist actions through private formations

43 /. Destruction and collapse of the education system

44 /. killing the national achievements of democracy

45 /. destruction of the social system

46 /. polarization of society

47 /. destruction of national values

48 /. destruction of the national culture

49 /. destruction of rights and freedoms

50 /. destruction of the middle class

51 /. increasing poverty and inequality

52 /. increase begging

53 /. Indebtedness of countries, governments through the IMF, WB, ECB

54 /. Dependence of the media - television, radio, newspapers, magazines,

55 /. Control, management of the drug business since the 18th century by the black aristocracy

56 /. Creating inequalities in society, managing these inequalities, destroying the middle class, with the ultimate goal of enslaving society.

57 /. Creating conditions for control and management of the economies of entire countries with the sole purpose of personal gain.

58 /. Creation of a university elite - a Masonic mafia-based global elite to rule states, and other institutions in favor of the Global Masonic elite.

59 /. Control and management of education in a country in order to blunt, greater control and management of the masses and the younger generation in order to zombie and manage and control at any level - emotional, educational, social and others.

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60 /. Creating a system for SOCIAL GENOCIDE MAFIOTISMUS

61 /. Control is the management of health care with the ultimate goal of reducing the population of the planet,

62/. Control and management of the system of drug development and dependence of the population on drugs.

63/. Control and management of patents and developments and elimination of scientists who created discoveries that can improve people's lives.

64/. Control and liquidate scientists, creators of drugs, but new methods of treatment that are cheap and hinder the wealth of the elite.

65/. Control and liquidation of scientists creating systems for zero-point generators and free energy generators.

66/. Control, management, drug production and addiction among the population with the ultimate goal of profit.

67/. Control, creation of GMO products, food, for the purpose of profit and reduction of the population.

68 /. Population control and management through food, lethal medicine, lethal vaccines, psychiatric medicines, deadly food, deadly grain, deadly sweeteners, GMOs, deadly water, air,

69 /. Control and management of the media, conquest of the media, and propaganda only of their goals, ideas, aspirations, plans, disguised under the slogan that care for humanity and the people in it.

70 /. Creating institutions that will govern countries, policies, such as the UN, UNICEF and others

71 /. Control of the special and secret services through their Freemasons to serve their lodges and personal interests, but not the laws of the respective state.

72 /. Establishment of their own structures, in which their members will be members who will later govern and head states - Foreign Relations Council, 1921 and branches - Institute for Pacific Relations - New York, Center for Foreign Policy Studies - Paris, foreign policy - Hamburg, Royal Institute of International Affairs -1920, Bilberberg Group - 1954, Club of Rome - 1968, Trilateral Commission 1973, to determine the international policies of states, to govern states.

73 /. Creation of an Elite by Universities of Global Masonic Mafia Elite - Yale University, Harvard, Columbia, Corel University, New York University, Sarah Lawrence College, Stanford University, University of Chicago, John Brapkins and others, University.

74 /. Control and management of all Masonic lodges - Knights Templar, Freemasonry, Rosicrucians, lodge of Gnosticism, Kabbalism, the Illuminati Freemasons through the principles of the Church of Lucifer.

75 /. Control and management of the elite and societies and states through Foundations - Rockefeller Foundation, Ford Foundation, Carnegie Endowment, Clinton Foundation,

76 /. Media management and control,

proprietary television - BBC, CBC, CNN, CBS, ABC, CNN and others,

telegraph agencies - the Associated Press, Reuters and others,

newspapers - New York Times, Washington Post, Wall Street Journal, Boston Globe, Baltimore Sun, Chicago Sun Times, Los Angeles Stays, Houston Post, Minneapolis Star / Tribune and others,

magazines. Fortune, Time, Life, Money, People, Newsweek, Business Week, Readers Ridge, US EU News and World Report, and others, dozens of publishers,

77 /. Propaganda and manipulation to reduce critical thinking

-- increasing the closedness, depression, dependence, feelings of slavery and dependence on the decisions and actions of the government

-- turning one's back on the real facts and evidence

-- dependence on propaganda

-- dependence on the promoted fear and stress

-- increase in mental illness

-- increase in drug abuse

-- increase in the number of homeless people

-- increase in the unemployed

-- increase in malnourished people

-- increase in malignant incurable diseases

-- increase in theft

-- increase in crime

-- increase in homicides

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- - increasing the bankruptcies of companies
- reducing the duration of

78 /. Control by the global Yamason mafia elite of each state and its management through the control and management of the special services and secret services of the respective state.

79 /. Control by the global Masonic mafia elite of all Masonic and other and all kinds of lodges of Freemasons around the world.

80 /. Control and management of the election, election and appointment of presidents, prime ministers, chancellors in the respective countries from the structures of the deep state.

81 /. Falsification of the elections in order to win the elections of this party, which is under the rule of global Masonic and mafia elite and the deep state. Managing the process of election fraud in countries where the global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state rule.

82 /. The global Masonic mafia elite rules, controls the deep state in every country on the planet.

The global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state it rules and its representatives act as a shadow government.

The global Masonic mafia flies and the deep state ruled by it does not respect the rights, freedoms, constitutions of the respective state, the treaties for the formation of alliances, such as the European Union.

In reality, the Global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state it rules uses the following undemocratic models of government as follows:

- Autocracy
- Oligarchy
- Plutocracy
- Kleptocracy
- Corporatocracy
- Cryptocracy

All these systems of government are managed on the basis of the principles of MAFIOTISM and the Financial Bank Resource Technological Mafia Materialism.

MAFIOTISMUS and the Financial Bank Resource Technological Mafia Materialized - THE IDEOLOGIES OF THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIOTIZED ELITE AND THE DEEP STATE

PRINCIPLES OF MAFIOTISMUS and the Financial Banking Technology resurset mafia Materialism -New TYPE OF GOVERNMENT IN PRIVATE AND PERSONAL INTERESTS- ideology of the GLOBAL Masonic mafia Elite And from its managed Deep State e in favor of the Global Masonic mafia elite

The differences between fascism and mafia.

State capitalism - is a system in which the state replaces private entrepreneurs in their role as factors - capitalists.

Under state capitalism, all property and all means of production are concentrated in the hands of one capitalist - the state, which in most cases is governed by the party elite and party nomenklatura.

The value added of production is redistributed by the sole capitalist, the state. It is often called either socialist or communist.

It is often argued that the countries of the socialist bloc are neither popular nor social, and that the economic system is in fact state capitalism.

Capitalism is an economic system in which production and trade are privately owned and managed by market economy methods, which in turn follow the principles of supply and demand. The main engine in such a system and supposedly "competition".

Fascism - professes the idea of a one-party state,. Fascism believes that nations and races are in constant conflict, Fascist governments forbid and suppress criticism and opposition to themselves.

They are opponents of class conflict.

Fascism is a state government similar to that of Mussolini, which elevates the nation and the race above the individual, establishes the one-party system, promotes nationalism, imposes strict economic and social control, applies violence, censorship

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The state is governed by the Prime Minister, if the same state is a parliamentary republic, which has set up and governs each state institution - ministry, state agency, manages both the executive and the judiciary through appointments close to him, and governs the legislature. power - the parliament.

The people are a mob according to mafia. Principles of crowd management: suppressing the masses to be guided by petty passions.

Creating problems of the "crowd" - the people through taxes, high prices, high interest rates on banking services, management of free funds of middle class citizens, thus through cunning and hypocrisy suppress the greatest human virtues - openness and honesty, which according to mafia are vices,

The rule of law - where the law begins, where it ends.

Exiled force of law, "liberalized" rights ",

The right of the strong,

Intervenes and removes all existing regulations and decrees

Mafiaism puts its hand on the laws, reorganizes the institutions, what is necessary and useful is only for their goals and aspirations.

MAFIOTISMUS and the Financial Bank Resource Technological Mafia Materialismus - THE IDEOLOGIES OF THE DEEP STATE AND THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA-DRIVEN ELITE

PRINCIPLES OF MAFIOTISM and the Financial Bank Resource Technological Mafia Materialism - THE NEW TYPE OF PUBLIC GOVERNMENT IN PRIVATE AND PERSONAL INTERESTS - THE IDEOLOGY OF THE DEEP MASS

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FORMULA OF THE MAFIOTISMUS

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The most simple model of the mafia which describes the factors which influence about the amount, type, and etc, of the mafia is the following:

MAFIOTISMUS = PERSONAL / GROUP / hidden and open/ Power / on the top of the state institutions / state and etc./ + Influence + Connections / to personal, private companies + Interests / personal, private, corporative / + ORDER / ORDERS + Personal Management of all state neveaus + Personal Control of all state niveausMafia structure / inside of or outside / + Monopolity Riegths + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility of taking an alternative decision - obligation - responsibilities - morality / ethics + Personal management and personal control of distribution of public state monetary and other resources / including European funds and funds /.

4. ELECTION COUNTERFEIT SYSTEM IN THE COUNTRY CONCERNED

SYSTEM AND ELEMENTS OF COUNTERFEITING, ELECTION CONTROL AND MANAGEMENT - TOOLS, before and after elections FROM THE DEEP STATE and the GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA_DRIVEN ELITE.

The typology of electoral fraud conducted as such in Bulgaria, fully supported by the United States, took place at the moment in Georgia, Michigan, Pennsylvania, Arizona, Nevada, Wisconsin, in fact on the states on which the election of the President of the United States depended.

The scams were:

- Voting of "dead souls"
 - Voting more than once
 - Expulsion of election observers during the counting of votes
 - Replacement of election protocols as documents with other ones with other different data
 - Falsification of election protocols and entry of other figures - incorrect and different from the real ones
 - Replacement of ballot bags with other ballots
 - The election officials from the commission filled in the ballots instead of the voters
 - Compromising machine voting and counting
 - Failure to enter the selection from the machine count in the election protocols
 - Acceptance of bulletins from the post office received after the legal deadline
 - Receiving ballots from the post office without identifying the voters
 - The number of deaths and non-living in one city / state exceeds those actually entitled to vote
 - Voting by persons with ID cards with their photo with data of persons living abroad
 - Voting by persons with ID cards with their photo with data of persons who have long since died
 - Voting by persons with ID cards with their photo, but with data of a person living abroad.
 - Voting by persons with ID cards with their photo, but with data of a person who is abroad
 - There are more voters by mail than those who have the right to vote.
 - Abuse of postal voting
 - Stop counting on election night at the same time before the end of election day.
 - Manipulation through computer systems for elections collecting election results.
 - Software manipulation of the vote counting through the counting system
 - Available software built-in ability to manipulate the results
 - Access of insiders directly to the machines and its software
 - Manipulation of the software even during its installation by the internal people of the election commission
- Programming voting machines to distribute more votes to Biden.
Machine programming anywhere in all states.
Counterfeit envelopes
Minutes in the minutes - uniform numbers of protocols for counting in the middle of the night in order to prepare ballots for Biden
Sending observers home due to suspension of the census
Prohibition of observers to observe the process of counting the ballots and preparation of election protocols
"Voting from the graves" - voting for dead souls, long-dead people

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Voting from nowhere "registered" voters

Voting people from one city / state to other cities / states

Retrospective ballots - anti-dating - return of the date of receipt

Found ballots allegedly sent by mail, but they are not folded and not placed in an envelope.

Multiple exceeding of the number of voters of the respective voters registered for voting in the respective town / village.

Instantaneous - per second jumps in "votes" for Biden in the software with hundreds of thousands of pieces, and not a single piece for Trump.

Vote buying - paying with money or other benefits to voters.

Buying votes by granting additional aid and financial incentives to the administration, which is under the control of the mafia.

Falsification of ballots.

Print more newsletters.

Printing fake newsletters.

Purchase and payment of electoral votes of entire ethnic groups of the population

Purchase and payment of electoral votes on the basis of race, ethnic group, refugees,

Creating parties that participate in the elections with the aim - a political fan - of winning the protest vote and dissolving the protest vote against a party that is governed and controlled by the mafia structure.

Elements of falsification in the protocols - identical serial numbers, lack of preferences, erroneous results, unaltered data,

Organizing all orders, semi-legal orders, secret orders, councils, committees, clubs, corporate capital companies, controlled media, controlled social networks, are choosing the "right candidate"

Creating a system, plan, program for compromising the "unwanted candidate" without selecting funds, morality, honor, dignity, morality.

Violation of the democratic principles of the state.

Controlled corporate vote -

Bought here

Repression of dissidents through the police

Repression through the prosecutor's office - filing meaningless complaints 4 times a day, calling the ungodly for explanations all day, especially at night,

The purchase of votes and the control by the police for compliance with the agreement, in case of non-compliance with the agreement, reactions follow.

Repressions through the prosecutor's office - pre-trial proceedings and prosecutorial inspections against opponents are activated. There are tens of hundreds of signals in the prosecutor's office against candidates who were never activated before the elections, but before the elections are activated, they are activated and repression follows. The systems of blackmail, of pressure, of extortion are used

Repression through the services. The secret services and others provide information through wiretapping and others, and an "enemy" is identified and the procedure is followed - compromising information in "accidentally caught" media.

The state revenue agency and the social security system are used for repression and pressure against business in order to use employees as a corporate vote. The State Revenue Agency launches audits, seizures of bail accounts, seizures of assets, seizes bank accounts for non-existent accounts

Various services attack business - fire inspections,, labor inspection, food inspection,

Repression through ministries - an example of repression through the Ministry of Agriculture of farmers farmers are important and control over them is a key element. Hundreds of thousands of people and families who work for them depend on these farmers. Prior to elections, subsidies are distributed to specific farmers to ensure that those who do not cooperate are subject to control, audit, repression and others.

Use of the border police system. Anyone who uses the information of the border police knows where the person concerned is, whether he is abroad or in the country. If he is abroad, his vote will be used as a third party will vote for him, using a fake ID.

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Control and management of the content in the protocols, feedback from the mafia.

The "disappearing voices" system - a pen with disappearing ink is used. Supporters of a mafia party enter the rooms and replace the pens with fading ink pens. After a while, the pens change to normal. Then again. This is how the process of "disappearance of votes" is managed. In this way, the votes of the opponents disappear. On the contrary, it grows on the mafia party.

FORGING PROTOCOLS WITH DISAPPEARING INK PEN

Providing funding for buying votes in elections - the black coffers of the ruling party - money received from racketeering, coercion, extortion, corruption schemes, smuggling, draining the budget, corrupt public procurement, draining European funds, draining state and European money through hoops from companies, robbery of state and municipal budgets,

Money laundering through - ordering advertising materials - issuing invoices at a higher value, paying advocates not at the real amount, but at a lower value, fictitious contracts with third parties - draining the party subsidy, invoicing fictitious services through fictitious civil contracts,

Repression and racketeering of a certain businessman, who must provide the appropriate number of votes, as they personally pay voters. Businessmen are extorted to pay voters, Businessmen are forced to do this by running the machine of repression by police services, state revenue agency, various inspection services, this is different from the controlled vote, here is a forced corporate vote.

Buying sociologists, political scientists, public figures, artists, public figures, economists.

Buying the above individuals through non-governmental organizations funded by the US state budget, such as the Open Society.

Creating protest movements against the "unwanted candidate". , supported by the global Masonic elite, their companies, NGOs and others.

Creating movements using differences in skin color, differences in sexuality, differences in religions and beliefs.

Creating movements / imaginary / of the citizens for progressive changes in the society / these are imaginary /.

Manipulation of the society through statements of ministers of defense, secret services, agencies and others that the "unwanted candidate" is a threat and danger to the national security of the state.

Presenting the selection of the "undesirable candidate" as illegitimate and preparing a program plan for its elimination as the impeachment procedure in the United States.

Given that the "unwanted candidate" is unmanageable and uncontrollable by the global Masonic mafia elite, mass measures are being prepared for compromising - false and untrue.

Given that the "unwanted candidate" is unmanageable, uncontrollable, society is manipulated that if he is elected, he will be killed.

Creating a plan program for complete compromising of the "unwanted candidate" election of the President - Prime Minister, for his compromising and delegitimization.

Paying party members not to vote for their candidate.

Threats, racketeering, extortion, of party members not to vote for their candidate.

Creating a plan to collect compromising information against judges, in which cases with complaints against the election results will be filed.

Creating a plan for overt and covert pressure on judges, where cases will be filed with a complaint against the election results and the election process.

Buying judges who will file cases with appeals against the election results and the election process.

Buying party members so as not to vote for their candidate.

Creating parties to win the negative vote and those who disagree with the policy of the "candidate wanted by the mafia", in order for the competing parties not to collect the percentage, which can be threatening. The so-called "political fan". Parties close to the mafia are stealing the negative vote to prevent the opposition from winning the election.

Preparation of a plan for discrediting the selected unwanted candidate "during his term, attempts to overthrow him, remove him, steps, compromising and others of constant harassment, coercion, extortion, in order for the" unwanted candidate "to obey, and to come under the control and management of a global Masonic mafia elite.

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Controls and management manipulation of propaganda through the media - television, radio, newspapers

Control and management of the pre-election process with compromising false and untrue against the "unwanted candidate" through the media - television, radio, newspapers, magazines, owned by the global Masonic mafia elite.

Preventing the "unwanted candidate" from presentations, company, disputes and others in the media - television, radio, newspapers, magazines, owned by the global Masonic mafia elite.

Creating a plan program for compromising, discrediting, vomiting false and untrue yellow compromising materials against the "unwanted candidate" in the media, owned by the global Masonic mafia elite.

Support for all movements, organizations, NGOs and others bought by the global Masonic mafia elite, or their property, to compromise the "unwanted candidate" in the media, owned by this elite.

Publication, presentation of untrue things, moments from the life and activity of the unwanted candidate "in the media, owned by the global Masonic mafia elite.

Control and management of manipulation and propaganda through SOCIAL NETWORKS - Facebook, Twitter and others.

Political campaigns through livestreams. Facebook is an auxiliary wheel in election campaigns. Especially in the context of a coronavirus pandemic, social networks are a powerful weapon and tool for election campaigns.

Social networks provide conditions for advertising.

But these ads are targeted to consumers according to their age, location and interests.

Newsletter numbers and others appear on social networks.

Target advertising to a specific problem and its solution. The so-called election problems.

For example, in the United States, the problem of weapons,

On the other hand, likes do not give an accurate picture of the interests of voters to a particular party. Separately, the likes may be more to one individual than the likes of certain parties combined.

In addition, when the likes pass a certain limit, the price of advertising on Facebook is lower. Facebook ads are raised every year.

Using organic posts to reach more people.

A post usually reaches less than 5% of those who like the page.

The use of "friends of friends" targeting - raising the number of people to reach the information.

Facebook provides an opportunity to make a policy for the period from election to election, not only before the respective elections.

This is a good condition for an endless campaign of the respective political party

The goal is constant contact with people. Livestreams and interactions are on the rise.

With constant activity not only during the campaign, when it comes more users more users are hooked on you and increases the possibility of publishing the candidate to go among the "recommended for you".

Live shows on Facebook with answers to questions from the candidate to various questions, even provocations.

When people share, comment, react, like, the algorithm again recommends publications from this candidate.

It is important whether they react and how they react and that they react.

Use of digital marketing.

Use the huge user database for the election campaign.

Those by interests, by interests by location, by age, by interests.

ACTIONS of the GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIOTIZED ELITE against the "unwanted candidate" in social networks.

Because social networks are owned by

OCCUPATION OF MEDIA BY ONE PARTY

The system is different for non-parliamentary parties as opposed to those of parliamentary parties.

Social networks are used by parties that cannot access television and radio, which are usurped by one or more mafia parties.

For non-parliamentary parties, social networks are the only media for advertising and campaigning.

There is one drawback to social networks - NO ONE CAN FOLLOW THE FINAL RESULT OF A CAMPAIGN.

Likes, shares and views are not necessarily converted into electoral votes

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USE OF THE PROXIMITY OF THE COMPANIES FROM THE SOCIAL NETWORKS WHICH OWNERS AND MANAGERS BELONG TO THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIOTIZED ELITE, FOR:

- Restriction of a candidate in the respective social network - Twitter, Facebook, Instagram
- Non-publication of posts and comments of the respective candidate on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram
- Prohibition of a candidate from publishing.
- Banning a candidate makes comments on Trump on Twitter and Facebook.
- Prohibition of a candidate for a certain period of time to make comments, publications and others.
- Stimulating the publication of negative and false publications, information, comments, publications, interviews for the candidate who is not wanted by the global Masonic mafia elite.
- Supporting the publication of negative and false information about unwanted candidates.
- Non-publication of positive achievements of the desired candidate.
- Publication of diplomas for the unwanted candidate
- Publication of yellow false news, information about the unwanted candidate.
- Manipulation of people through false, incorrect publications, information, commentators of the unwanted candidate.
- Corporate ban on the unwanted candidate

LAUNCH OF COLOR REVOLUTIONS to change governments with a government of loyal people of the global Masonic mafia elite and the deep state

Funding protests, clashes with the authorities through non-governmental organizations funded by the US state budget, such as the Soros Open Society.

Buying sociologists, political scientists, public figures, artists, public figures, economists

FINANCING a party abroad to win certain elections

FINANCING a party by an oligarch from the global Masonic mafia elite or from companies of the deep state

ABDICATION OF THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM - THE COURT

ABDICATION OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE

5 /. THE FRAUD AND COUNTERFEITING OF THE US 2020 ELECTIONS in USA organized from the DEEP STATE and its manager – THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA-DRIVEN ELITE

The United States has entered a deep political, economic and moral crisis.

The foundations of American democracy, which boasted that it is not just a model, not just an example, not just a proof of the most developed and indisputable democracy, have really been undermined.

The events around November 3, 2020 became censorship in well-defined media and social networks, there was organic pluralism, in the democratic discussion

There are also proven election frauds.

Similar election frauds have been committed in Bulgaria since 2013, and the government has learned about these frauds from certain US structures.

The United States undermined the name of a great nation that seemed to serve as an example.

The United States undermined the name of a nation that boasted of its democracy and set its democracy as an example.

The United States promoted its democracy and based on that they IMPORTED DEMOCRACY IN OTHER COUNTRIES. Based on boasting of the best DEMOCRACY, the United States made YELLOW REVOLUTIONS in different countries.

AND AT THE SAME TIME, REALLY, THEY DID NOT IMPORT DEMOCRACY, BUT IMPORTED CORRUPTION SCHEMES, IMPORTED FICTIONAL IMITATION OF DEMOCRACY.

US ELECTIONS PROVE THE EXISTENCE OF A FICTIONAL IMITATION OF DEMOCRACY

The typology of electoral fraud conducted as such in Bulgaria, fully supported by the United States, took place at the moment in Georgia, Michigan, Pennsylvania, Arizona, Nevada, Wisconsin, in fact on the states on which the election of the President of the United States depended.

The scams were:

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- Voting of "dead souls"
- Voting more than once
- Voting without identification
- Expulsion of election observers during the counting of votes
- The election officials from the commission filled in the ballots per kilogram
- Machine voting and counting have been compromised
- Acceptance of bulletins from the post office after the legal deadline
- Receiving ballots from the post office without identifying the voters
- The number of dead and non-living in one state exceeds those actually entitled to vote
- There are more voters by mail than those who have the right to vote.
- Abuse of postal voting
- On election night, counting stopped at the same time in the disputed states of Georgia, Pennsylvania, Michigan, Arizona Nevada, Wisconsin,
- And the next moment the numbers who voted for Biden jumped by tens of hundreds of thousands of voters for Biden without a single vote for Donald Trump
- Forensic audit of some of the voting machines in Antrim, Michigan, proved the transfer of 6,000 votes from Trump to Biden
- Proven software manipulation of the vote count is the registration of votes for Biden in favor of Biden
- Available software built-in ability to manipulate the results
- Access of insiders directly to the machines and its software
- Manipulation of the software even during its installation by the internal people of the election commission
- Electoral fraud was organized in all states
- Programming voting machines to distribute more votes to Biden.
- Machine programming anywhere in all states.
- Counterfeit envelopes
- Stop counting in the middle of the night to prepare ballots for Biden
- Sending observers home due to suspension of the census
- "Voting from the graves" - voting for dead souls, long-dead people
- Voting out of nowhere "registered" Americans
- Voting of people from one state to other states
- Retrospective ballots - anti-dating - return of the date of receipt
- Found ballots allegedly sent by mail, but they are not folded and not placed in an envelope.
- Multiple exceedances of the number of Americans registered to vote.
- Instantaneous - per second jumps in "votes" for Biden in the software with hundreds of thousands of pieces, and not a single piece for Trump.

FOLLOWERS OF BIDEN AND TRUMP on Facebook, TWITTER

Biden's followers in the wind - 20 million.

Trump's followers on Twitter - 88.8 million

Biden's followers on Facebook - 7.78 million

Followers of Trump on Facebook - 34.72 million

With these data, it is somehow unthinkable to get such election results as they come out

The purpose of these scams was to steal Trump's "red states" and make the vote more widespread. In this way, large-scale fraud is covered up.

In reality, honesty in the choice was violated.

If an election is uncertain, the election is declared discredited.

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Election observers were isolated, removed from the opportunity to monitor the actions of election officials in the counting of ballots.

Election observers are placed 30 to 50 meters or more from the places where the census takes place

In some places, they are invited to leave the polls, even to go home, because they have stopped the counting process.

Despite all the evidence, the censorship of social networks Facebook, Twitter and free media overflowed with evidence - recordings,

Hundreds of witnesses signed affidavits to notaries describing the violations

Georgia The number of dead and non-living in the state who voted in the election exceeds the actual number of eligible voters

Those who voted by mail are more than those who have the right to vote.

Biden wins Georgia, which is an all-red state "for Donald Trump with a red governor and a red legislature, which is virtually impossible.

Pennsylvania lacks 47 memory cards with more than 50,000 votes.

In Pennsylvania, 1.8 million ballots were mailed to voters and 2.5 million ballots were counted. This is a difference of 700,000, a proven fraud.

THE MAFIOTISMUS in the state structures - they refuse to check the signatures,

This will show whether the ballots sent by mail have been submitted legally.

VOTE BY MAIL

The problems with voting by mail arose after the authorities sent ballots to everyone on the voter lists, not just to those who explicitly asked because they wanted to vote.

Many ballots on which they never voted at all were collected by the Democrats and sent on their behalf voting for the Democratic Party.

That is why the signatures need to be verified.

Authorities did not allow or allow an audit of all machines regarding machine voting

Authorities did not allow an audit of the machines where there was software manipulation in Biden's favor.

Arizona state senate requests to audit these scams were not allowed. There was actually sabotage by the state election commission.

This is real resistance

Already in the 2005 report of the Center for Electoral Reform "To increase confidence in the electoral process" Baker - Carter point out:

- The great dangers of reduced control when voting by mail
- Ability to manipulate the machines
- Ability to manipulate the census

In reality, not only legitimate votes are counted,

Election fraud in the United States is the rule rather than the exception,

Members of the election commission change ballots, and this was led by specific people

Before the election, such people were trained

FAKE BALLOTS

There are no special security elements in the bulletin - a seal or a watermark.

The counterfeiter simply creates his own ballots by running them through a copier.

But reverse envelopes are "safer ballots."

Because the envelope cannot be copied, so it must be from a real voter.

Another scheme - Participants go door-to-door to voters and persuade voters to allow them to take their completed ballots and send them on their behalf as a public service. So they take the sealed envelopes and take them home where they open them on steam, replace the real ballot with a fake one and seal the envelope.

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. Then, for greater security, they are scattered in different mailboxes so as not to attract this attention.

PARTICIPATION IN POSTMANS

If there is a postman who is an opponent of Trump, he can do the following⁷

"Throw the ballots in the trash if he knows they're for Trump."

- To delay them and restrict them after the end of the election day
- In this way, ballots never reach the polling stations

VOTE BY MAIL

During the mail voting, bilateral supporters collect and count the ballots in the local election commissions, deciding which ballots are valid and which should be discarded due to irregularities.

ELDERLY HOMES AND HELPING ELDERLY PEOPLE TO VOTE

This is a great opportunity to receive fake ballots and return ballots.

In some nursing homes, nurses are hired agents who go from room to room and they fill out the ballot, which is for one candidate, but this is not the candidate who asked to be reported by the elderly person in the nursing home.

There are situations when Uzhkim civil servants help foreigners in their homes to fill out the ballot.

IN THE POLLING STATIONS EXPULSION OF THE OBSERVERS OF THE OTHER CANDIDATE

When they are removed or expelled even from the room and not only 5-10 meters, the observers who represent the other candidate

For example, when the ballot is folded at this angle, it is valid for "our" candidate and it is valid or corrected.

After mixing these ballots, they are mixed with the others and cannot be distinguished, and thus valid votes become

FAKE VOTERS

People vote in polling stations where no ID card is required. For example, Pennsylvania is such a state.

Another option is to fill in cards with the name and area of that person and give them to a third person to go to the polls to vote.

Organized counterfeiters reproduce the signature of the person they are voting for.

Newsletters are sent by mail, but people who have long since died.

Bulletins are issued a fhora who do not live in this village at all. For example, paradoxes arise when, for example, there are 350 voters in one settlement and there are 670 ballots for that area.

VOTE BRIBERY

Homeless shelters are one such source of voters who easily get corrupt.

FRAUD AT SOFTWARE LEVEL THROUGH THE ELECTION SOFTWARE SYSTEM

PROGRAMMING MACHINES TO DISTRIBUTE MORE VOTES for Biden

Really ascertained from space.

The counting of US elections is done through software systems outside the US. This is done in Frankfurt am Main and Barcelona through Dominion Voting System and SUUTL - a European software company based in Barcelona. It offers purpose-based voting systems. World.

Until its inception, the system has proved vulnerable to electronic manipulation.

George Soros is the head of the Board of Directors of DOMINION.

Apart from that, Microsoft co-founder RAUL ALLEN has invested \$ 40 million in SCUTL.

The main shareholder and holder of most of the shares in SCUTL is the husband of Nancy Pelosi, who is chairman of the US Senate, whose nephew is the governor of California.

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On December 2, 2020, DOMINION received \$ 400 million from the Chinese government through a Chinese bank in Switzerland.

It has been proven that, through this system, the 7 million votes that were for Trump were transferred to Biden.

Apart from that, 3 million people who died and were born and lived in the middle of the 18th century voted for Biden, and both ballots and ID cards were printed in China.

On election day, November 3, 2020, President Trump sat in the Eisenhower Hall of the White House on a 4-screen screen and watched everything happen.

On these screens, each bulletin was tracked thanks to the QUANTUM BLOCKCHANE system.

The official ballot for the November 3, 2020 elections was marked with a very complex radioactive isotope watermark that can actually be traced from space.

The US government, after determining that this server of the DOMINION participates in the change of votes. After the order, the server was found in Frankfurt.

November 9 saw the dismissal of Secretary of Defense Mark Esper and the appointment of Christopher Miller, a former director of the National Counterterrorism Center.

On November 7, 2020, CIA Director Gina Hasped was arrested in Frankfurt am Main.

On November 4, after the election, the Department of Defense, the 305th Battalion, and the National Security Agency (NSA) recorded evidence of real-time fraud to change votes in Georgia, Michigan, Nevada, Arizona, Wisconsin, and Pennsylvania.

Frankfurt am Main is home to the CIA's largest overseas cybercenter. It is the largest overseas structure outside the United States. There is a cyber attack against the cyber center. These actions hit the elite, the oligarchy, the mafia, key structures working against the US constitution, as the center ensured the theft of votes from Trump and these votes were transferred to Biden and also falsified.

The fact that in five critical states of the United States at the same time the counting of votes was stopped at the same time by someone's order, shows that the work of election commissions is managed by external forces violating the Constitution.

CIA Director Gina Haspel led these falsifications of election results.

It has been declared treason.

All of these actions point to Obama and Biden.

In addition, the director of the US Agency for Cyber and Infrastructure Security CISA Creech Krebs was accused of treason and fired.

The military operation in Frankfurt was led by General Richard Clark, who was born and raised in Stuttgart into a military family and who knew Stuttgart, which is 150 km away, very well. Far from Frankfurt.

He commanded the operation as commander of the US Special Operations Headquarters in Florida. In Wiesbaden, which is close to Frankfurt, is the command center of the American troops in Europe and uses premises, buildings with an area of 12,000 sq.m. This is a US military intelligence center. This server contains information on who ordered the election commissions to stop counting and who ordered the activation of the software for transferring votes from Trump to Biden.

According to General McKinney, President Trump must and must declare a state of emergency in the United States under the 1807 Uprising Act. , which allows the deployment of troops in the United States to suppress lawlessness and initiate the immediate arrest of criminals., participated, organized, conducted, rigged the 2020 elections.

This law has been enacted six times in US history. Movements such as "We the people - wi du people insist on this action.

This event was not noticed by the media at all // Iskra Lukanova /.

MAFIA ORGANIZATION - MAFIOTISMUS OF US STATE STRUCTURES

This whole structure is organized and managed by a trusted member of the candidate, as he organizes training of his agents, controls his agents, contacts with his agents as at the higher level, if someone asks a question, then the lowest level of agents has nothing to do and they have not contacted, they do not know, they do not know the person who is at the higher level.

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This is the nimble mafia organization, hierarchically organized in several levels, and the upper level is in contact with everyone from the lower level, and on the horizontal level people do not even know each other.

This is a precisely structured, mafia organization.

The above evidence proves:

- 1 /. Mafiotismus in the CIA in favor of the group around Biden
- 2 /. Mafiotismus of Special Forces
- 3 /. Mafiotismus in the Ministry of Defense and especially at the highest level - Minister
- 4 /. Mafiotismus in the US Cyber and Infrastructure Security Agency
- 5 /. Mafiotismus of all structures involved in the election process, election commissions and others.
- 6 /. Mafiotismus in public services such as the post office.
- 7 /. Mafiotismus in other government services

ABDICATION OF STATE STRUCTURES - MAFIOTISMUS AND CORRUPTION PRACTICES

Even with this evidence of fraud, there was an abdication of such institutions as FBI, CIA, NSA, Department of Homeland Security.

These are all institutions that are run by the elite and are subordinated to the elite, to the mafia
These institutions protect only the elite, not the law.

ABDICATION AND BLOCKING OF THE JUDICIARY - MAFIOTISMUS OF THE COURT DEPENDENCE OF JUDGES on any

The Ministry of Justice's refusal to comply with US law.

The refusal of judges to hear appeals with indisputable evidence of fraud attached.

GROSS VIOLATION OF THE LAWS OF AMERICAN VALUES

Courts at all levels and in all states up to the US Supreme Court have refused to rule on the merits without considering the evidence.

Real mafiaization of the court:

- Refusal to examine evidence
- Pronunciation without substance
- Pronunciation without reasons
- Judge's political statements
- Violation of the constitution
- There is a cover-up of illegal actions of the government
- Refusal to issue an institutional response to complaints doubts evidence evidence of fraud
- Legitimate denial of justice, blockage of justice

ORGANIZATION AND COORDINATION

The goal of this organization is to remove Donald Trump, due to his actions for 4 / four years in his term.

RESTORATION OF GLOBALISM THROUGH MAFIOTISMUS

FAILURE OF DEMOCRACY AND THE LEGALITY PROVING FICTIONAL IMITATION OF DEMOCRACY LAWLESSNESS,
CORRUPTION, MAFIA in the country, at all levels, positions

MEDIA CENSORSHIP of the media owned by representatives of FBRTMmaf Materialism.

- Negatively reflects President Trump
- Impartial coverage of Trump

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- Refusal of airtime of important news and arguments. in pro-Trump and against Biden on Democrat and elite television
- Millions choose
- Mass fake media
- Mass yellow news
- Lack of information
- Refusal to be informed about important events with the Trump administration
- Refusal to be informed about the achievements of the Trump administration
- Refusal to be informed about important events of the Trump administration

CENSORSHIP IN THE SOCIAL NETWORKS MAFIOTISMUS THEM, of the five companies Twitter, Google, Facebook, in favor of the MAFIA in the country

- Negatively reflects President Trump
- Impartial reflection
- Refusal to cover important news and arguments. in pro-Trump and anti-Biden
- Millions choose Trump's speeches
- Mass fake media
- Mass yellow news
- Lack of information
- Refusal to be informed about important events with the Trump administration
- Refusal to be informed about the achievements of the Trump administration
- Blocking people who like Trump
- Block these people and ban them from writing about Trump
- Refusal to be informed about important events of the Trump administration
- Block Trump's comments
- Censorship of written comments by Trump
- Rubbing Trump's comments

THE THEFT OF THE PRESIDENCY THROUGH THE MEDIA AND THROUGH MAFIOTIZED STRUCTURES at the state level in all structures.

6. CITIZENS 'SURVEYS AFTER US 2020 ELECTIONS

The result of 90% of polls and inquiries to US citizens about the election they openly state that the election was rigged November 2020 POST ELECTION SURVEY surveyed and surveyed 1,750 Americans from 7 questionable states.

Knowledge test for information in 8 states

82% of the vote for Biden they know to him and his mistakes in life - lack of information

17% do not know the facts that would reverse the result - burying the bad news about Biden

- Media censorship of Biden scandals
- 15.4 do not know about the accusations of Terra Ryde, for rape in 1999 by Biden.
- If they had known, 8.9% would not have voted for Biden.
- 45.1 5 of those who voted for Biden did not know about the scandals with Biden's son
- Censored on Twitter and Facebook
- If they knew 9.4% would vote for another.

25.3% of those who voted for Biden did not know about the Left Ideology and Vice Presidential candidate Harris - otherwise 4.1% would not have voted for Biden

Hiding Trump's success

"About the pandemic."

- Workplace

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- For economic development and level
- 39.4% of those who voted for Biden did not know about Trump's achievements, then 5.4% of them would not vote for Biden

Trump's foreign policy

43.55 of Biden voters do not know about Israel's foreign policy achievements agreement with third countries

36.1 of those who voted for Biden did not know about Trump's actions to promote vaccine research, 5.3% of them would not vote for Biden

50.5 "of those who voted for Biden did not know about Donald Trump's policy in energy, expansion of drilling in the seas and the Arctic - 5.8% of them would not have voted for Biden then

49% of those who voted for Biden did not know about the economic jump in the United States based on the actions of President Trump, so if they knew, 5.8% of them would not vote for Biden.

7. WHY IS DONALD TRUMP HATRED FROM THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA-DRIVEN ELITE AND THE DEEP STATE? WHY THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA-DRIVEN ELITE, THE DEEP STATE, THE MAFIA, THE OLIGARCHY, THE GLOBALISTS, THE CLEPTOCRACY PREPARED FRAUD AND COUNTERFEITING THE US ELECTIONS 2020

- 1 /. He is against the elite
- 2 /. He is against corruption
- 3 /. He opposed the elite
- 4 /. He took action against the elite
- 5 /. He took measures against the pedophilia of the elite
- 6 /. He took measures against the abuse of children by the elite
7. He took measures against the forcible extraction of adrenaline from children.
- 8 /. He created new jobs
- 9 /. He is against globalization in all its forms
- 10 /. He opposed the elite who replaced and erased the history of America
- 11 /. He opposed the elite who are destroying American monuments.
- 12 /. He opposed a project like New Work 1619 that portrayed all white Americans as racists
- 13 /. He opposed discrimination
- 14 /. He opposed the Liberal ideology.
- 15 /. Trump did everything for all Americans, ordinary people
- 16 /. Trump protected ordinary Americans from the tyranny of the elite over them.
- 17 /. Trump has created new jobs.
- 18 /. Trump has returned many productions to the United States and created new jobs, which is against the globalism of the elite
- 19 /. Trump has made sure that all international deals that are not in the interest of the United States are reviewed, and he has made sure that they are in the interest of the United States.
- 20 /. Trump is against wars. Trump has not started a single war
- 21 /. Trump has returned thousands of US troops to the United States from Afghanistan
- 22 /. Trump refused to start a war against Iran and other countries.
- 23 / Trump is against the NEW WORLD ORDER
- 24 /. Trump is against the plan to IMPOSE THE NEW WORLD ORDER through the pandemic and chopping he knows about
- 25 /. Trump is really the only obstacle TO ADJUSTING THE NEW WORLD ORDER
- 26 /. After Trump's entry into the White House, he stopped the SOROS project and the representative of the Financial Banking Resource Technology Mafia Materialism for the transfer of hundreds of thousands of REFUGEES from Africa and the Middle East, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Iraq, and other countries to Europe and Europe for social system of European countries.
27. Trump stopped funding the World Health Organization after proving wrongdoing, dependent on its funding foundations and companies and governments - such as China. Trump refused to pay more to the World Health Organization

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28 /. Trump found discrepancies over the obligations of NATO member states and found that only the United States pays its contributions to NATO and that other member states either do not pay the respective contributions or that the contributions do not correspond to the corresponding percentage of the country's Gross Domestic Product.

29 /. Trump spoke about the Paris Agreement.

8. DONALD TRUMP IS AGAINST THE INTRODUCTION OF A NEW WORLD ORDER foem the GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA-DRIVEN ELITE AND THE DEEP STATE

UN DOCUMENT FOR A WORLD ORDER

The plan concerns the period 2021 - 2020

THE PLAN IS FROM SEPTEMBER 21, 2001, BY Rabbi Amon Yitzchak

1. World Government - SP
2. Cashless world currency
3. World Central Bank
4. Global military force
5. End of national sovereignty
6. End of private property
7. End of the family unit - family
8. Decimation of the population - a penalty for every 10th for discipline
9. .Control of growth and population density
10. Mandatory vaccination - for the purpose of biological control and genocide
11. Universal basic income, salaries are canceled
12. Microchip implantation for payment and monitoring
13. Social rating system
14. Device for monitoring and biological control Article 5D
15. Raising the children of the SP schools and universities are the property of the SP
16. Termination of private transport - without owning private cars
17. All companies become the property of the JV
18. Restriction of air traffic
19. Concentration camps - creation of agglomeration centers
20. Elimination of irrigation systems
21. Elimination of private agricultural holdings
22. Closure of private agricultural pastures
23. Removal of single-family houses
24. Limited use of agricultural land
25. Prohibition of natural medicines - herbs
26. Prohibition of natural treatments
27. Prohibition of fossil fuels

To be held from 2021 to 2030.

Home Special operation Crown virus

9. DONALD TRUMP IS AGAINST THE GLOBALIZATION supported and managed by the GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA-DRIVEN ELITE AND THE DEEP STATE

Donald Trump's trade wars against China have hurt Globalization.

At the UN meeting in September 2019, Donald Trump said.

10. WHAT DID TRUMP INTRODUCE AND ACHIEVE AGAINST THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIA-DRIVEN ELITE AND THE DEEP STATE IN USA?

1. Before each cabinet meeting he prays to Lord!

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2. He returned the greeting "MERRY CHRISTMAS! Mery Christmas which was banned and replaced with Happy Holidays!
3. Cancel the opportunity to KILL NON-BABY CHILDREN after the 6th month of pregnancy!
4. Removed Gender locker rooms and toilets in schools and public buildings! \
5. Break down the biggest networks for PEDOPHILIA, CHILD TRAFFICKING for SEX, ORGANS, and BLOOD!
6. Ensure peaceful relations with Iran and North Korea!
7. Removed over 1000 administrative barriers and restrictions for businesses and citizens!
8. Before the PLANNING PANDEMIC, America had the LOWEST UNEMPLOYMENT in its history!
9. Save your own production by imposing RESTRICTIONS AND RESTRICTIONS on China and Mexico!
10. WHICH INTERNATIONAL AGREEMENTS DID THE US COME FROM IN THE TRUSTEE OF TRUMPET

Exited the Paris Climate Agreement

As early as 2017, Trump announced his intention to abandon the implementation of the document as early as June 2017, THE REASON - THE INJUSTICE of this agreement and the threats of losing several million jobs in the United States

As early as January 23, 2017, the Donald Trump administration refused to participate in the Trans-Pacific Partnership TTP agreement, on the third day of his inauguration as president. The United States joined the TTP in 2008. , since then negotiations have been under way to conclude a new agreement based on the TTP. At the same time, other countries were involved in the TTP.

As a result, on February 4, 2016, it provided for the creation of an area for free movement of goods, services, capital and technology. This agreement was signed by 12 countries in the Pacific. However, Donald Trump says the document provides unreasonable benefits to US competitors. This agreement does not fully take into account American interests.

NORTH AMERICAN AGREEMENT TO FREE TRADE

On January 23, 2017. President Trump signs a decree to begin negotiations to reform the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) with the participation of the United States, Mexico and Canada.

This agreement was signed in 1994. . For Trump, this agreement is a "bad deal" and "the worst trade deal in history."

This has led to job cuts and wage cuts in the United States due to the influx of cheap labor from Mexico and the transfer of many manufactures and entire terrorism industries to neighboring countries.

Trump warned that if a revision of the agreement did not work, the United States would pay to unilaterally withdraw from the agreement.

On November 30, 2018, all three NAFTA members sign a new trade agreement called the US-Mexico-USMCA Agreement - on July 1, 2020 this agreement enters into force.

11. JOINT PLAN ON THE IRANIAN NUCLEAR PROGRAM.

Trump avoided the war against Iran that the elite dreamed of.

12. Trump refused to pay money to the World Health Organization because he found corrupt practices

13. Trump has put pressure on US partners in NATO because they do not pay their annual contributions, and their annual contributions do not correspond to the relevant percentage of the country's Gross Domestic Product.

14. PROTOCOL ON THE MANDATORY RESOLUTION OF DISPUTES TO THE VIENNA CONVENTION OF 1961

15. AGREEMENT for liquidation of medium-range and short-range missiles V DRSMO

16. OPEN SKY AGREEMENT on May 21, 2020

17. The United States is withdrawing from the Paris Climate Agreement because President Trump said the whole program was a scam and a corrupt money laundering scheme.

18. SALE OF WEAPONS

19 /. THE TRADE AGREEMENT BETWEEN THE UNITED STATES AND KATAI

11. PROMISES OF DONALD TRUMP IN THE 2016 ELECTIONS

Donald Trump's promises in the 2016 elections:

70-year-old businessman Donald Trump becomes the 45th president of the United States. He won the election based on his promises to the Americans, which were:

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1 /. Normalization of relations with Russia. Establish good personal relations with Russian President Vladimir Putin. Donald Trump believes that it is necessary to cooperate with Russia in the joint fight against Islamic State, in resolving regional conflicts - Syria and other regions and resolving the situation in the Middle East. For such cooperation, he is ready to give up US support for Ukraine, the rebels in Syria and even the support of European NATO member states.

2 /. Destruction of Islamic terrorism. Donald Trump plans and plans to convene an international conference to fight radical Islam. As allies in this struggle, he considers the countries of the Middle East - Egypt and Jordan, and as a major ally - Israel. Donald Trump plans and aims not only to defeat the Islamic State but also to behead "Al Qaeda. He also plans to stop and eliminate all sources of funding for the terrorist organizations Hezbollah and Hamas, with Iran as the main sponsor.

3 /. Tax cuts. Donald Trump promises to ease the tax burden for all Americans. This is especially true for the middle class and business, reducing the maximum income tax rate from 39% to 33%.

In addition, Trump predicts changes to the progressive tax scale by reducing the number of tax rates from seven to four. Births with an income of up to \$ 29,000 will be exempt from income tax.

Trump also promised to introduce additional deductions for childcare and inheritance tax, as well as reduce the corporate tax rate from 35% to 15%.

4 /. To protect the United States from illegal immigrants

Donald Trump is in favor of radical changes in immigration law that do not ease the procedure for obtaining immigration rights. Donald Trump wants to impose harsh measures on countries that refuse to readmit their citizens who have been deported from the United States.

In this connection is the promise to build a wall on the border with Mexico - over 600 kilometers, as well as to ban the entry of people in the United States who profess Islam.

5 /. Refusal of unfavorable commercial transactions.

Trump condemns and opposes the Trans-Pacific Partnership, the North American free trade agreement between the United States, CANADA and Mexico.

Donald Trump's goal is to create jobs in the United States. He believes and is ready to support any such trade agreements that will create for the creation of jobs in the United States. It will aim to achieve a review of the conditions in force since 1994. North American Free Trade Agreement between the United States, Canada and Mexico NAFTA. He is ready, even if he does not reach more favorable conditions, to terminate this contract and this agreement

The same goes for the TPP Trans-Pacific Partnership

6. Firm foreign trade policy. Based on the data that show a negative US foreign trade balance with some countries such as China. It will aim to balance trade relations between the United States and China, so that the United States can benefit, not just China.

DECISION-MAKING ISSUES AND THE VIEW OF DONALD TRUMP AND JOE BIDEN

7 /. Remove the Obama Care program.

Donald Trump promised on the first day of his presidency to abolish the health care reform program or Obamacare. Trump's goal is transparent pricing of both drugs by pharmaceutical companies and health programs. Trump has promised not to cut spending on health programs for older and poor Americans.

In addition, his plan is to transfer to the competent state authorities all the powers to manage, control the program of social assistance to the poor.

8/. - Creating opportunities for poor children to access prestigious schools

Donald Trump believes that every American family, regardless of income, should be able to choose a school for their child. He promises to provide \$ 20 billion in federal subsidies for the children of low-income families.

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9 /. Eliminate corruption and weaken the power and monopoly of the media

Trump will take action against the merger of business and politics time. Trump intends to ban members of Congress and administration officials from holding lobbying positions for five years after leaving office.

Donald Trump seeks to reduce the number of civil servants.

Donald Trump promises to prevent the monopolization of media resources and turn them into conglomerates that are able to manipulate public opinion in favor of certain pressures and business forces. Mostly it is for the television networks NBS, ABC, SNN. The latter are really close to the Democratic Party.

10 /. Preservation of the death penalty and the right of citizens to bear arms

11 /. Legalization of marijuana

12. PRINCIPLES of the MAFIOTISMUS in USA

The differences in fasism and mafiotismus.

State capitalism - is a system in which the state replaces private entrepreneurs in their role as capitalist factors.

In state capitalism, all property and all means of production are concentrated in the hands of a capitalist - the state, which is in most cases governed by party leadership and party nomenclature.

The assigned value of the production is redistributed by the sole capitalist - the state. It is often called either socialist or communist.

It is often argued that the countries of the socialist bloc are neither folk nor social, and the economic system is actually a stagnant capitalism

Capitalism is an economic system in which production, trade is privately owned and governed by market economy methods, which in turn follow the prnces of supply and demand. The main engine in such a system and supposedly "competition".

PRINCIPLES OF MAFIOTISMUS - THE NEW TYPE OF STATE GOVERNANCE IN PRIVATE AND PERSONAL INTERESTS

The state is governed by the Prime Minister if the same state is a parliamentary republic that has put in place and directs each state institution - a ministry, a state agency, manages both the executive and the judiciary through appointments that are close to him, and manages the legislative power - the parliament.

The people are a crowd according to mobbing. Principles of crowd control: suppressing the masses to be guided by petty passions.

Creating problems for the "crowd" - the people through taxes, high prices, high interest rates on bank services, management of the free means of citizens from the middle class, thus, through trickery and hypocrisy, the greatest human virtues are suppressed - honesty and honesty, which, according to mafia, are vices,

The rule of law - where the law begins, where it ends.

Gentle law enforcement, liberal rights,

The right of the strong,

It interferes and removes all existing arrangements and regulations

Мафиотизма puts a hand on the laws, reconfigures the institutions, the necessary and useful is only for their purposes and aspirations.

FORMULA OF THE MAFIOTISMUS

The most simple model of the mafia that describes the factors that affect the amount, type, and etc of the mafia is the following:

MAFIOTISMUS = PERSONAL Power / on the top of state institutions / state and etc./ + Influence + Connections / to personal, private companies + Interests / personal, private, corporative / + ORDER / ORDERS + Personal management of all state neveaus + Personal Control of all states niveausMafia structure / inside or outside / + Monopoly Riegths + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility of taking an alternative decision - obligation - responsibilities - morality / ethics + Personal management and personal control of distribution of public state monetary and other resource (including European funds and funds).

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The mafia is also available for the public and private sector. The power of the mafia and the corruption practices in Greece in the public sector are very stark.

THE MAIN PRICE is the material or non-material benefits of members of the above-mentioned structures. Here is the connection BETWEEN THE MAFIA AND THE CORRUPTION

SPHERE OF THE MAFIA all over the world.

The mafia in Greece can be found in all spheres of the public live.

Sphere of Appearances of the Mafia: 1 /. In the state administration, 2). In politics, 3). In the justice system, 4). In the police, prosecutor, 5 /. In public services., 6 /. In the private sector, 7). In the TV, radio, television, newspaper, and etc., 8 /. In the citizen sector.

The political, financial and weapon producer mafia is the main reason for the beginning of the war in Iraq.

The slowness, the instability, the inconsistency of the "crowd" - the people, their inability to understand and feel the conditions of their own lives.

The power of the mob in the service of mafiaism is blind, unwise, unwise, serving to the left and to the right.

Mafiaitis makes suggestions for freedom equality, brotherhood, justice - pushing to debauchery, drunkenness Trickery, hypocrisy, violence, robbery and terror.

Terror takes place on all vertical and horizontal structures of the executive.

Terror is in favor of mafia and its representatives from the prosecutor's office, the judiciary.

Terrorism is carried out through the NRA, the Ministry of the Interior, the Prosecutor's Office, tax offices, municipal offices and others.

Mafiotismus has the most important factor in public thought - print and print media, all types of media - mostly television and the Internet.

The crowd's thought moves through the press and the media. The role of the press and the media is to be: to sense the needs, to transmit the complaints and to reveal the dissatisfaction of the people. The seal proclaims free speech. But that's obvious. News events are managed and controlled by representatives of mobbing.

Hunger and degeneration of the masses

With constant demands, constant spending, constantly increasing costs, taxes, uninterrupted indebtedness - hunger, taxes, obligations - give birth to slave dependence that governs the crowds, and their hands and minds are blocked for a different thought.

Liberalism

When the people conceive that they are making concessions and indulgences in the name of his freedom, he realizes that he is authoritative and raises against the valley. The people are like a blind man, who encounters all sorts of obstacles, problems, helpless looking for a patron - a support that is not as if he does not think he returns to his first position - puts his rights obediently in his authority .

Specula is a basic form of business and business relationships.

Capital is the one that moves the world, moves, and the slavery that controls the industry and trade

Weakened public thought. - those who ponder and oppose, need to learn to meditate, the mental forces must turn to a verbal shootout of legal time and blasphemy.

Societies must be deceived and deceived and manipulated

Chaos in public thought. Civil society is replaced and replaced by NGOs funded by the Mafia, and civil society is practically implemented and implemented

To lose any opinion on political issues in the forefathers, and political issues are not within their competence of society, but only by those who direct the game.

Another strategy - people's flaws, habit, passions, rules of relationships, to yell so much to create a chaos that does not go out.

People cease to understand each other and they do not have to, to deny the people to think on political issues for their solving.

Personal initiatives must also be confronted - one against another - to make sense.

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Monopolies destroy wealth. Capital humiliates agriculture.

Increase in wages and simultaneous increase in prices. Raising wages is not beneficial to workers, because at the same time prices will be increased, the rise in commodity prices, and sometimes the rise in wages. Representatives of mafiotismuss hold public forces. They are the legislators, they determine the composition of the court and they give away justice, they punish, they pardon, they judge. They hold all these positions in their hands

The Mafiotismus holds in his hands the unbridled ambitious, insatiable, greedy, ruthless of vengeance, the evil, the hateful, the envious.

Mafiotismus employs state institutions, education, education, municipal structures and all kinds of government, creates bourgeois arbitrariness, affects the rule of law, with liberal arbitrariness arbitrariness.

Consciously complicate and confuse legislation.

Judges do not do the law, no one can punish them, no one wants to punish the judges, no such institution to punish them, sanction them, fire them.

Mafiotismus and its representatives at the state level create and support the PROCESS OF THE BOGOLIVED IN THE COURT AND THE PROCUREMENT. Judgments that misrepresent the interpretations, contradict the law and its proper execution, create a precedent in a judicial system that does not allow the right of the court, create a precedent law that grossly violates the laws and rights of individuals and companies, decree contradictory interpretations.

Mafiotismus and their representatives affect the judiciary, electoral institutions, the press, the media, the freedom of person, education, and education as the cornerstones of free life.

The institutions are fragmented and divided the power of the state - the legislature, the executive and the judiciary. If one part is damaged, the whole state and its actions are also damaged. The state has suffered from the lack of justice, the lack of implementation of the law by judges, the lack of law enforcement by prosecutors.

The real blood of the state is poisoned - when the judiciary is poisoned. That country is best ruled by the Mafia.

"The Mafia places and appoints judges and prosecutors. The three pillars of chaos are in full dependence on mafios.

Mafia Control and Corruption Control in the Judicial System, - Court and Prosecutor's Office, Administration, Ministries. Appointed people who have something dark in the past, a mistake in their lives, violations of laws, an affair, a crime. Such persons are faithful and do all things to which they are commanded to execute orders, orders, for fear of being denigrated. They seek to preserve their privileges, authority, gains, honor, power, power, their rights to do what they want without being punished.

Destruction in the constitutions of everything that interferes with the mafia and pushing them into what seizes the very content of constitutions and citizens' rights.

Corrupt anti-corruption institutions are being set up, which are initiated by representatives of mobbing, but do not actually enforce the laws but conceal the crimes of their members and servants,

Depleting the population and citizens in their own daily problems of survival.

Dealing with the population. Real deprivation of the rights and freedoms of citizens demonstrated in the constitutions and their replacement into other subordinates in immutability.

Real destruction of citizens 'freedoms in other laws and the actual deprivation of citizens' rights and freedoms in the constitution.

This leads to the confiscation of all rights, so that the laws will prohibit and resolve only those things that are in the interest of the mafia and their personal interest.

The whole press and all the media have been briefly controlled by mafia people.

Persons with a different mindset will not be allowed to scent to media, television, radio, newspapers or magazines.

PUBLIC RESOURCE CONTROL SYSTEM

It is about controlling public funds at the level of prime minister and ministers, so that these public funds go only through companies close to the prime minister and to the respective ministers and report a percentage of the profits from these public funds.

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COMPLETE SYSTEMS.

In this way and with these methods, judges and prosecutors, statesmen, officers, ministers

THE LEGISLATION SYSTEM

By means of auditing acts of revenue and other government agencies, tax offices that prove violations, obligations of individuals and companies in particularly large sizes, companies and persons will be kept in subordination, not presenting these documents, and will be kept on logs ready to run every time and use against the person or company concerned.

REAL CREATION OF AN OPTION

Who will make seeming attacks and protests The real firefights on political and any level will be in vain and fake.

CLOSING AND ADJUSTING CANCELLATION BY MAFIA IN PROSECUTORY

In order for the mafia to work in the prosecutor's office, the top of that organization should be the mafia.

DISPOSAL OF THE ATTENTION OF THE IMPORTANT POLITICAL PROBLEMS

DISTRIBUTION OF PUBLIC AWARENESS OF SERIOUS ISSUES.

KILLING THE LAWS, PRESSING THE POWER OF THE LAW.

- Not to enforce the laws.
- Breach of laws to the detriment of rivals, enemies of the mafia.
- Legalization of crimes committed by prime ministers, ministers, mafia people.
- Free interpretation of the laws.
- Free execution of laws, depending on the client, the people and the mafia companies.
- Settlement of lawsuits in favor of the mafia and the people in the utter violation of laws and principles of law.

ESTABLISHING LAWS TO ADAPT THE REPRODUCTION AND DEMOCRACY AND THE RELIEF AND LEAVING OF COMPANIES FROM MAFIA - THE GOVERNMENT.

IMPLEMENTATION OF MAFIA ORDERS IN ALL COURTS and in the PROSECUTOR OFFICES.

THE ADMINISTRATIVE COURTS WILL APPROXIMATE THE CRIMES OF THE EXECUTIVE AUTHORITY, GOVERNMENT, MINISTERS, MINISTERS-PRESIDENT.

THE ADMINISTRATIVE BODIES WILL TERMINATE THE DEFENSE AGAINST STATE INSTITUTIONS, MINISTRIES, MINISTERS, MINISTERS - PRESIDENTS, - WHICH HAVE ALREADY DID NOT TAKE OFF CRIMES.

APPOINTMENT OF JUDGES AND PROSECUTORS IN FAVOR OF MAFIA.

ESTABLISHING INSTITUTIONS TO CLOSE CRIMES, BREACHES OF LAWS BY JUDGES AND PROSECUTORS

Judges perform only mafia orders, honest citizens and businesses to lose cases.

Judging is done only on the basis of executing the orders of the Mafia.

Selection of judges and prosecutors only after receipt of orders and the conclusion of an agreement that they will execute mafia orders.

Applying the law by judges and prosecutors will follow the principle of mafia order, not law enforcement.

Judges and prosecutors are appointed only if they belong to the mafia.

Establish institutions and inspectors who will not punish the lawlessness and crimes committed by Mafia judges and prosecutors.

Fear of non-ascension, unrelated to the rank of judge or prosecutor.

Creating conditions for lifting and raising judges, police officers and prosecutors in rank - the single fulfillment of mafia orders.

CREATION OF STRUGGLE AND CLEARANCE IN THE COURT, MINISTRY OF INTERIOR PROTECTION IN THE HOME. CREATION OF STRUGGLE AND UNREGULAR REMEDY OF ALL AND ALWAYS ONLY IN FAVOR OF MAFIA. ABSOLUTE AS PRINCIPLE OF POWER

REMOVAL OF CASSATION LAW. In the Bulgarian Art. 280 of the CCP - Inclusion of cassation law in the power of the ruler and the mafia.

The seal will fall under the strict censorship of the Mafia only for its benefit.

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Real use of all media and print media tools in favor and in the interest of the Mafia.

Different treatment of laws by judges and prosecutors.

Criminal proceedings against people belonging to the Mafia will be dealt with in their favor in violation of any legal provisions.

Criminal proceedings against people - opponents of the government's mafia - will be resolved in violation of the laws to their detriment and their ruin - both intellectually, physically, mentally.

A halo of governmental infallibility and "non-violation" of the laws will be built.

A system of government-infallible laws will be created despite their ubiquitous violation.

Violation of the laws of citizens' rights and freedoms by government, ministers, state institutions, will remain unpunished by both the court and the prosecution.

13. CONCLUSION

In this article we prove the elements of how the global masonic mafia-driven elite and managed from its deep state can manage the elections and the falsification of elections around the world. And on examples of the ELECTION 2020 in USA.

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